

CENTRAL ASIA AND JAPAN: FUNDAMENTALS AND PROSPECTS OF STRATEGIC PARTNERSHIP DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. The following issues are analyzed in this scientific article: the significance and historical role of establishing diplomatic relations between the Republic of Uzbekistan and Japan. The huge role of ratification of the strategic partnership agreement between two countries is also shown.

The peculiar specifics of the political system of Japan, including the nature, structure and basic functions of the parliament and the procedure for holding parliamentary elections, the place and role of the emperor's institution in the political system, as well as the cabinet of ministers, are examined.

The article considers the basis of the principle of forming the Cabinet of ministers, its role in the process of reforming the political system of society, the features of the political system, in particular the formation of a multi-party system, the reasons for success as a dominant party - the Liberal Democratic Party of the country, the role of the LDP in the process of modernization of the Japanese political system, the role of the Cabinet of ministers in the political system of society, the government's program for the development of the country's economy, as well as the specifics of the practical implementation of this program, the activities of the parliament and the cabinet to amend the Constitution of the country.

At the same time, Japan's foreign policy in Central Asia, especially in Uzbekistan, bilateral and multilateral diplomacy with the countries of the region were analyzed. The stages of development of Japan's cooperation and investment policy with Central Asian countries were studied comparatively. The prospects of Japan's bilateral relations with Uzbekistan are forecasted and development trends are analyzed.

Keywords and expressions: political system of Japan, parliament, political party, Constitution, cabinet of ministers, modernization, dominant party, the House of Representatives, the House of Councillors, political development. Cooperation with Central Asian countries. "CA + J" format. Foreign economic relations and investment policy.

MARKAZIY OSIYO VA YAPONIYA: STRATEGIK HANKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ASOSLARI VA ISTIQBOLLARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu ilmiy maqolada quyidagi masalalar tahlil qilinadi: O'zbekiston Respublikasi va Yaponiya o'rtasida diplomatik munosabatlar o'rnatilishining ahamiyati va tarixiy roli. Shuningdek, ikki davlat o'rtasidagi strategik hamkorlik to'g'risidagi bitimning ratifikatsiyasi muhimligi ko'rsatib o'tiladi.

Yaponiyaning siyosiy tizimiga xos xususiyatlar, jumladan parlamentning tabiati, tuzilmasi va asosiy funksiyalari, parlament saylovlarini o'tkazish tartibi, imperator institutining siyosiy tizimdagi o'rni va roli, shuningdek, vazirlar mahkamasi faoliyati o'rganiladi.

Maqolada vazirlar mahkamasini shakllantirish prinsipi, uning jamiyat siyosiy tizimini isloh qilishdagi roli, ko'p partiyaviylik tizimini shakllanish xususiyatlari, mamlakatdagi Liberal-

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demokratik partiyaning hukmron partiya sifatida muvaffaqiyatining sabablari, Yaponiyaning siyosiy tizimini modernizatsiya qilish jarayonidagi roli, vazirlar mahkamasining siyosiy tizimdagi o'ziga xos jihatlari, parlament va vazirlar mahkamasining mamlakat Konstitutsiyasiga o'zgartishlar kiritish borasidagi faoliyati tahlil qilinadi.

Shu bilan birga, Yaponiyaning Markaziy Osiyodagi, xususan O'zbekistondagi tashqi siyosati, mintaqa davlatlari bilan ikki va ko'p tomonlama diplomatiyasi tahlil qilinadi. Yaponiyaning Markaziy Osiyo davlatlari bilan hamkorligi va investitsiya siyosatining rivojlanish bosqichlari taqqoslab o'rganiladi. Yaponiyaning O'zbekiston bilan ikki tomonlama munosabatlar istiqbollari prognoz qilinadi va rivojlanish tendensiyalari tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Yaponiyaning siyosiy tizimi, parlament, siyosiy partiya, Konstitutsiya, vazirlar mahkamasi, modernizatsiya, hukmron partiya, Vakillar palatasi, Kengashlar palatasi, siyosiy rivojlanish. Markaziy Osiyo davlatlari bilan hamkorlik. "CA + J" formati. Tashqi iqtisodiy aloqalar va investitsiya siyosati.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is known that since the beginning of 1992, diplomatic relations have been established between Uzbekistan and Japan based on the principles of mutually beneficial and equal friendly cooperation.

On July 29, 2002, the Republic of Uzbekistan and Japan signed a Joint Declaration on Friendship, Strategic Partnership and Cooperation. The Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 8, 2002 "On measures to further develop cooperation with Japan" played an important role in the effective development of strategic partnership between the two countries.

It should be noted that on the basis of these political initiatives and mutual agreements, ample opportunities have been created for the consistent development of cooperation between Uzbekistan and Japan. As a result, strong ties have been established between the two countries, based on the highest political and institutional foundations of modern international relations.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, "Today, Japan is one of our most important and priority partners in modernizing the economy of Uzbekistan and socio-economic development of our country.

We are grateful for the support provided by our Japanese partners, and are interested in further expanding investment, financial and technical cooperation, developing direct contacts and fruitful cooperation between the business circles of Uzbekistan and Japan"².

It should be noted that in the Address of the President Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Parliament of Uzbekistan on January 24, 2020, it was noted that Japan, along with other countries, plays an important role in the system of priorities of foreign policy of Uzbekistan.

As stated in the Address of the President, "We will continue the large-scale work begun to intensify the foreign policy of Uzbekistan, the path of open, pragmatic and well-thought-out foreign policy that meets our national interests. We will further strengthen our partnership, long-term and multifaceted partnership with all countries"³.

These conceptual ideas put forward by the head of our state, in turn, serve as a source of strengthening the base of new potential opportunities for the development of strategic relations between Uzbekistan and Japan.

² Greetings from the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Prime Minister of Japan Shinzo Abe on the 25th Anniversary of Diplomatic Relations between the Republic of Uzbekistan and Japan) // Xalq so'zi (People's word newspaper) 2017-yil 27-yanvar, №20(6714)

³ Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis) // Xalq so'zi (People's word newspaper) 2020-yil 25-yanvar, 19 (7521)

It is known that in the development of relations between countries in the political and other spheres, the commonalities in their political system, in particular the closeness of interests in the strategy of political development, will play an important role. Features of the national strategic directions and goals of the political systems of Uzbekistan and Japan, such as based on the principles of democratic development, peace, cooperation, stability, innovative development, serve as the basis for bilateral relations.

Improving the political system of our society on the basis of the most modern and effective democratic criteria and the implementation of strategic goals for the accelerated development of our country on its basis have been identified today as the leading criteria for the development of our country.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Legislation, regulatory framework, intergovernmental agreements, scientific articles, expert opinions were used in the preparation of this article. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the Action Strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis, the Constitution and laws of Japan, government decisions served as important sources.

The following scientific articles published in scientific journals were also used: Kalmichek P., Pavlenko P. "The political system of modern Japan" (Aspect Press, 2017. p.7.); Inoguti T. "Japan's political science development" (Polis, 2019, №4. P.60.); Molodyakova E. "Japan: total conservative victory" (Problems of the Far East, 2018.. №1. P.182.); Varyushin P., Tixotsnaya I. "Political Modernization in Japan - Impacts of European and American Practices"(Asia and Africa today, 2016. №7.); Dadabaev, T. Japan's Search for Its Central Asian Policy: Between Idealism and Pragmatism (Asian Survey, Vol. 53, p. 508.); Len Ch. Central Asian Diplomacy: Motivations, Implications and Prospects for the Region (The China and Eurasia Forum Quarterly.vol.3, № 3, p. 130.); Fumitaka Furuoka. A History of Japan's Foreign Aid Policy: From Physical Capital to Human Capital. (School of Business and Economics, Universiti Malaysia Sabah, 2007. p. 21.); Nazarmuhamedov B. "Japan's ODA Policy Toward Central Asia and the Caucasus. An Analysis of Japanese Assistance to Economic Development in Kyrgyzstan and Armenia" (Journal of International and Advanced Japanese Studies, Vol. 10, March 2018, p. 183.); Information on the topic in the media was also used.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

Our core method is a qualitative, systemic, comparative, sociological, institutional, case study approach drawn from a synthesis of peer-reviewed literature as well as current reports and documents related to our theme. The system method helped determine the role of the political system of countries in the global political process, allowed to identify the relationship between countries. The comparative method made it possible to comparing the foreign policy strategies of countries. The sociological method was necessary to identify the dependence of the foreign policy priorities and economic relations of countries on other areas of society: foreign and domestic policies, geopolitical and national characteristics, the economy as a whole, etc. The institutional method was applied in analyzing the institutional and legal framework of relations between the two countries. The historical method helped to study the evolution of the development of the Japanese political system, the stages of the process of political modernization and to identify the main stages of development of diplomacy and investment policy of Japan and to make predictions about the future course of the country. The case study method made it possible to investigate with concrete examples stable and temporary conditions and circumstances affecting the formation of mechanisms for diplomacy and investment activity, to determine the degree of dependence between various participants in this process.

4. RESULTS / ANALYSIS

The article shows that the foreign policy of countries is inextricably linked with their political system on the example of Japan and the Republic of Uzbekistan. The dynamics of the process of political modernization in Japan and the importance of the Japanese experience for Uzbekistan are studied. The priorities of Japan's foreign policy strategies towards Central Asia and Uzbekistan, investment policy and economic and energy diplomacy are analyzed. As a result, the prospects of bilateral relations are forecasted.

5. DISCUSSION

At present, the Japanese government is in the process of further improving the country's political system, expanding and modernizing its democratic foundations.

It should be noted that the Japanese political system has many unique features that are unique in many ways. "Japanese are tolerant of political processes based on the cultural and geographical features of their country"⁴. This aspect is important in the political development of the Japanese state and the improvement of the political system of society. The Constitution, adopted on November 3, 1946, served as an important legal basis for the formation of the modern Japanese political system. It is known that this document came into force on May 3, 1947 and is still in force today.

The Constitution of Japan has the status of the Basic Law of the country, according to which the Japanese people are designated as the leading entity exercising state sovereignty. According to the Japanese Constitution, democratic principles of political power apply. Based on the advanced ideas of constitutional law, "in the last quarter of the twentieth century, the process of democratic renewal in Japanese society has reached its peak. During this period, the third wave of democracy will intensify"⁵.

Reforms in the Japanese political system are playing an important role in achieving such results.

The role of parliament in the Japanese political system is immense. In fact, Japan has the oldest tradition of parliamentarism among Asian countries. Of course, the political processes that took place after the Second World War, the measures taken to implement democratic reforms had a strong impact on the formation of the Japanese political system, including the parliament, which is an important part of it.

According to Article 41 of the Japanese Constitution, "Parliament is the supreme and sole legislative body of state power and consists of two chambers: the House of Representatives and the House of Advisers.

The House of Representatives is the lower house of the Japanese parliament and is elected for 4 years. The House of Advisers is the upper house and is elected for 6 years. At present, every three years, half of the deputies of the upper house are re-elected in accordance with Article 46 of the Constitution⁶.

The House of Representatives consists of 480 deputies and is responsible for reviewing and approving key bills.

The Constitution of Japan provides for a very wide range of powers of the Parliament. In addition to its main functions in the field of legislation, finance and oversight, the parliament has the authority to ratify international treaties, initiate amendments to the country's constitution, establish an impeachment court, and participate in the formation of certain executive bodies.

⁴ Kalmichek P., Pavlenko P. *Politicheskaya sistema sovremennoy Yaponii*. (The political system of modern Japan) – M.: Aspekt Press, 2017. p.7.

⁵ Inoguti T. *Razvitie politicheskoy nauka Yaponii* (Japan's political science development) // *Polis*, 2019, №4. p.60.

⁶ Kalmichek P., Pavlenko P. *Politicheskaya sistema sovremennoy Yaponii*. (The political system of modern Japan) – M.: Aspekt Press, 2013. p.58-59.

At the same time, it should be noted that the appointment of the Prime Minister of the country, as well as the adoption of laws and the state budget are the most important tasks of parliament.

The role of the Prime Minister and the Cabinet of Ministers in the Japanese political system is unique. The Cabinet of Ministers is the leading body exercising executive power. That is why the cabinet is often referred to as the Japanese government. The level of participation of the executive branch in the legislative process is much higher. Ninety percent of the bills passed by the Japanese parliament are bills submitted by the government.

This means that in Japan, the executive branch serves as the leading subject of the political process, although it operates within the framework of the democratic division of power into sectors.

The role of political parties in the exercise of political power in Japan and in the Japanese political system in general is enormous. It is political parties that are an important political institution that develops strategies for changes in Japanese political life and ideas of political development.

The party, which has a majority in parliament, forms the central and local authorities. At the same time, it will have the right to lead the Cabinet of Ministers.

In the process of reforming Japan's political system, the country's top political leaders have sought to create a unique model of governance in recent years, as well as to adopt progressive aspects of the European and American political systems. At the same time, the Japanese political system does not deny the national traditions and values of the Japanese people.

The role of the country's constitution in the Japanese political system is incomparable. At the same time, the Constitution, which came into force in 1947, is being seriously amended to make changes and additions to it, based on the needs of the country's political development.

"During 2019, the Japanese government has begun to take concrete steps to review the constitution. In particular, the task of amending the electoral norms, expanding the powers of the authorities, reinterpreting Article 9, which sets the norms for the organization and use of the Japanese armed forces, is becoming more urgent"⁷.

At the same time, the issues of modernization of relations between political parties in Japanese society, the introduction of effective institutional mechanisms that ensure the consensus of political parties on leading issues of national importance are also on the agenda.

Indeed, the political parties operating in Japan are ideologically very close to each other. Therefore, experts conclude, Japan can achieve a two-party system of government based on a relentless pursuit of an effective political system.

At the same time, the foundations of "consensual" democracy in Japanese society are being strengthened on the basis of modern principles of coalition government. Today, the Japanese government is in the process of increasing the efficiency of the country's political institutions, reforming the country's political system in line with modern needs.

This means that today the Japanese political system is going through a period of significant improvement. The modernization of the political system, in turn, paves the way for the opening of new sources for political development.

Central Asian countries, especially Uzbekistan, play an important role in Japan's foreign policy. In addition, the region plays an important geopolitical role as a "bridge" between East and West. Central Asia is located between Russia and China, South Asia, the Middle East and Europe, and is historically a region where the Great Silk Road passed⁸.

⁷ Rossiya i mir: 2019. Ekonomika i vneshnyaya politika (Russia and the world: 2019. Economics and foreign policy) // Mirovaya ekonomika i mejdunarodnie otnosheniya, 2019. №5. p.130.

⁸ Dadabaev, T. Japan's Search for Its Central Asian Policy: Between Idealism and Pragmatism // Asian Survey, Vol. 53, p. 508.

For Japan, the strategic and geoeconomic importance of the region is as important as other regions of Asia, including Southeast Asia. The amendments to Japan's Blue Book on Foreign Policy in 2018 are a key strategic conceptual document, according to which the Ministry of Foreign Affairs describes Central Asian diplomacy as follows:

"For Japan, Central Asia is of great geopolitical importance, ensuring peace and stability in the region, supporting socio-economic development, development of investment activities are important areas of Central Asian diplomacy. The priorities of Japanese diplomacy in Central Asia are:

- 1) strengthening bilateral relations;
- 2) Development of regional cooperation and contribution to the solution of regional problems through the "Central Asia + Japan" dialogue;
- 3) development of cooperation on a global scale⁹.

A comparison of the Central Asian version of this document in previous years shows the strategic importance of the region, the priorities of Japan's regional diplomacy have gradually developed and significant results have been achieved at various stages. Based on the priorities of Japan's Central Asian diplomacy, the chronology of relations can be divided into the following five periods:

1992-1997 - establishment of diplomatic relations, sending the first missions. This period is explained by Japan's support to accelerate market transition reforms in the region, support Central Asia's membership in regional development banks, the launch of the Japanese Government's Official Development Assistance (ODA) program, and Japanese companies' interest in Central Asia's energy infrastructure projects. Japan's White Paper on Energy Policy (1993) emphasizes the importance of diversifying energy resources and Central Asian resources¹⁰.

1997-2001 - With the adoption of documents such as Prime Minister Hashimoto's Eurasian Diplomacy and Prime Minister Obuchi's Silk Road Action Plan, Japan's policy in Central Asia was conceptualized. For the first time, the strategic directions of cooperation with Central Asia and the Caucasus were clearly defined. In June-July 1997, K.S. A large delegation of political, business and academic circles led by Obuchi visited Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan. One of the main topics of the talks was to discuss the direction of investment in the energy sector.

2001-2009. Japan's policy in Central Asia has changed in the wake of US military action in Afghanistan and the Middle East. The Koizumi-led government's foreign policy vector has focused on peace and stability and security in the region. Established in 2004, the CA + J communication format remains the central platform for multilateral cooperation to this day. In 2005-2006, a foreign policy group led by Taro Aso, the foreign minister of the Koizumi and Abe governments, promoted the concept of "Freedom and Prosperity" calling for the promotion of democratic values in various regions of Eurasia and the Middle East. According to concept, Japan has expressed solidarity with Western countries in strengthening democratic values in various parts of the world. The new power balance has weakened China's position in the region and prompted Tokyo to consider the possibilities of economic, primarily energy, projects in the region. Japan's energy strategy has begun to pay special attention to the countries of the region. Japanese companies have begun to take an active part in oil and gas projects in the region.

2009-2012. Japan's abandonment of the concept of "freedom and prosperity" has led to some improvement in relations with China. The government, led by Yoshihiko Noda, has given priority to Japan's resource diplomacy in Central Asia. Abroad, uranium mining and nuclear

⁹ MOFA Diplomatic Bluebook 2018, p. 149.

¹⁰ Len Ch. Central Asian Diplomacy: Motivations, Implications and Prospects for the Region // The China and Eurasia Forum Quarterly. vol.3, № 3, p. 130.

cooperation have developed rapidly. However, since the Fukushima events in March 2011, the country has undergone significant changes in domestic and foreign energy policy.

The modern period from 2012 to the present is explained by the further intensification of Japan's pragmatism and resource diplomacy. Japan's policy in Central Asia during this period differed in terms of developing business ties, intensifying major energy and investment projects.

The Japanese government's conceptual approach to Central Asia is being put into practice. Japan has become an important international partner for the countries of the region pursuing a multifaceted foreign policy. There are agreements on friendship and cooperation, strategic partnership between Japan and Central Asian countries. The absence of an unresolved international problem and disagreement between Japan and Central Asian countries is one of the positive factors contributing to the successful development of political relations.

Japan's presence in Central Asia has been supported in two main ways. The first direction was implemented in the form of grants, technology cooperation, low-interest and interest-free loans and other types of financial assistance. Japan's Official Development Assistance (ODA) program has provided significant support to lay the foundation for sustainable economic development, support democratization and transition to a market economy, and develop the social sector. The second direction provided for the active participation of Japanese business in promoting economic interests in the region. In this regard, Tokyo has sought to contribute to the development of energy-related projects in Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan, which have oil, gas and uranium, and has ensured the export of these energy sources to Japan¹¹.

After the end of the Cold War, Japan presented to the world a new Charter on the Basic Principles of Official Assistance for Development.

These principles include:

- Development and environmental protection are interrelated;
- The use of military assistance is excluded;
- The development of the military industry in the host countries should be monitored;
- Strive to develop the principles of democracy and market economy¹².

In general, Japan's foreign policy in Central Asia has served not only as a key tool to ensure regional development, but also to establish bilateral relations and support Japan's foreign policy goals in the countries of the region¹³.

At present, the most important features of Japan's diplomacy in Central Asia are economic and resource diplomacy, modernization of regional infrastructure, including the promotion of Japanese infrastructure exports, focused on human resource development.

It should be noted that the long history of cultural ties between our peoples has had a great positive impact on the development of friendly and cordial relations between Uzbekistan and Japan during the years of independence. Today, due to the consistent democratic reforms implemented by both countries and the commonalities in their enormous results, the positive prospects of modern cooperation are showing.

Interparliamentary ties are actively developing through holding forums with the participation of the parliamentary friendship leagues "Japan Parliamentary League for Friendship with Uzbekistan" and "Democratic Party of Japan - Uzbekistan". Since 2002 political consultations are held on a regular basis between the foreign ministries of the two countries. Uzbekistan and Japan cooperate in solving various international problems and have similar

¹¹ Dadabaev, T. *Japan in Central Asia: Strategies, Initiatives, and Neighboring Powers*. – Palgrave Macmillan, 2016. p. 20.

¹² Fumitaka Furuoka. *A History of Japan's Foreign Aid Policy: From Physical Capital to Human Capital*. School of Business and Economics, Universiti Malaysia Sabah, 2007. p. 21.

¹³ Nazarmuhamedov B. "Japan's ODA Policy Toward Central Asia and the Caucasus. An Analysis of Japanese Assistance to Economic Development in Kyrgyzstan and Armenia", *Journal of International and Advanced Japanese Studies*, Vol. 10, March 2018, p. 183.

views on many issues of world politics. Uzbekistan supports the entry of Japan into the permanent members of the UN Security Council.

Today, Japan's relations with Uzbekistan have reached the level of strategic partnership. Japan recognizes Uzbekistan as a regional state influencing the situation in Central Asia. In relations between Tashkent and Tokyo, special attention payees to cooperation in the "Japan + Central Asia" format. Japan supports Uzbekistan's regional policy aimed at creating a reliable and close neighborly environment in Central Asia.

An important role in the development of trade and economic relations is played by the Uzbek-Japanese and Japanese-Uzbek committees on economic cooperation.

In the period from 1991 to 2007, Japan put forward the following initiatives:

- 1993 - The Initiative for the Inclusion of Central Asian Countries in the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development - enabled the countries of the region to receive financial and other assistance, in particular the Official Development Assistance Program (ODA);
- 1997 - Eurasian diplomacy, which envisaged the intensification of economic and political cooperation between Japan, Russia and Central Asia. Three main principles: mutual benefit, trust and long-term perspective;
- 1998 - Program of Action on "Silk Road Diplomacy" aimed at supporting democratic reforms, promoting economic reforms, reconstruction of transport infrastructure and exploration of natural resources;
- 2004 - Central Asia plus Japan Initiative - regular meetings at the level of heads of ministries and departments to promote cooperation and regional interaction;
- 2006 - "Transformation of Central Asia into the corridor of peace and stability" - an approach to Central Asia taking into account the long-term perspective, supporting open regional cooperation, searching for a partnership based on common universal values.

In fact, these initiatives have been of great importance for the countries of the region, and, together with ODA assistance, currently amounting to about two billion dollars, have really contributed to the development of Central Asia.

In August of 2008. The intergovernmental agreement "On liberalization, mutual protection and promotion of investments" was signed, which entered into force on September 24, 2009. 10 joint ventures have been established in Uzbekistan, incl. one with 100% Japanese capital, and 11 representative offices of Japanese companies are accredited. The volume of mutual trade turnover between Uzbekistan and Japan is growing dynamically. As a result of 2014 bilateral trade amounted to 189.5 million US dollars.

Total amount of financial and technical assistance to Japan amounted to more than \$ 3.4 billion. Thanks to Japan's financial and technical assistance, a number of socially significant and infrastructure projects have been implemented in Uzbekistan in the areas of health, education, energy, transport, telecommunications and other areas.

In the development of economic relations between our countries, the main task is to expand cooperation in the field of foreign trade, investment and finance. The volume of foreign trade does not yet correspond to the available potential, but it should be noted that there is direct air communication between our countries twice a week. Of particular importance is the further development of cooperation in the energy sector and tourism.

A new priority direction in the development of economic cooperation between Uzbekistan and Japan is the sphere of innovation. Following the visit of Prime Minister Shinzo Abe to Uzbekistan in 2015, a lot of work was done to create the Japanese-Uzbek Youth Innovation Center with the participation of universities in both countries. This center opens unique opportunities for the development of mutually beneficial relations between our countries, taking into account the availability of rich resources of Uzbekistan and high technologies and innovative ideas of Japan.

Following the meeting of the Foreign Ministers of Central Asia and Japan in the spring of 2017, was adopted a "road map" for regional cooperation in the field of logistics and transport.

At the same time, Japan attaches great importance to Uzbekistan to implement its regional policy in Central Asia. For example, Uzbekistan accounts for 57% of Japan's aid to the region. Japanese companies are closely cooperating in the processing of mineral resources of Uzbekistan. It should be noted that as a result of measures taken by the governments of the two countries in the energy sector, the oil refineries in Bukhara and Fergana have been restored, and the Kokdumalak gas compressor station has been built.

The main areas of our economic cooperation are electricity, oil, gas, and chemicals. Supply of turbines and other energy technologies for Uzbekistan's energy systems is one of important area for Japanese business.

During his official visit to Japan, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev also touched upon the issues of energy cooperation between the two countries. Currently, 11 Japanese companies have representative offices in Uzbekistan. To date, 65 billion yen has been invested in the development of Uzbekistan's energy sector through Japan's Eximbank.

Uzbekistan is an important transit center in the region, and special attention is paid to projects in the field of communications. Toyota Tsusho has signed a \$ 100 million loan agreement with the National Bank for Foreign Economic Activity to finance data transmission and Internet speed projects.

CONCLUSION

Assessing the results of Japan's diplomacy and investment policy in Central Asia, we can conclude that for Japan, Central Asia is not only a geopolitically important region, but also a large resource base and a promising market.

Japan's investment strategy envisages special attention to loans, grants, economic and technological assistance, infrastructure and energy mining and processing projects to Central Asian countries. Japan also pursue an active foreign policy aimed at promoting democracy and market relations in the Central Asian region.

At the same time, the analysis of the country's regional policy in recent years requires a transition to a more active foreign policy in Central Asia, the widespread use of socio-economic and financial-investment tools.

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